

Clinical Profile of Severe Acute Malnutrition and Vitamin B12 Status in Children Aged 1 Month to 60 Months: A Prospective Observational StudySubhajit Dutta¹, Amita Austin Haems², Vaishali Satija³, Suresh Chandra Goyal⁴, Vivek Parasher⁵¹Resident, Dept of Paediatrics, Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur²Resident, Dept of Paediatrics Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur³Resident, Dept of Paediatrics Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur⁴Professor, Dept of Paediatrics Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur⁵Professor, Dept of Paediatrics Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur

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Abstract:

Background: India has the greatest population of severely under-nourished children in the world and accounts for over 20% of under-five childhood deaths every year. Much emphasis is placed on folic acid, iron, and other macronutrients, not Vitamin B12. This study was thus done to determine the clinical profile of SAM patients and the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency and clinical manifestations in children with SAM aged 1 month to 5 years of age.

Methods: A hospital-based, observational, prospective study on 95 children suffering from severe acute malnutrition (SAM) aged 1-60 months. A detailed socio-economic, feeding, and development history was obtained, and a complete anthropometric evaluation was performed. Blood samples were sent for measurement of plasma vitamin B12.

Results: The study included 95 children with Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM), with an equal gender distribution (50.52% male, 49.47% female) and most children (81.05%) being under three years old, 72.63% of the children were from lower socio-economic classes. A significant portion (72.63%) came from rural areas, and 77.89% of the children had anemia, with 28.42% having severe anemia. Macrocytic hypochromic anemia was the most common type (48.42%). 77.88% of the children had deficient Vitamin B12 levels, with deficiency more prevalent in males, children from lower socio-economic backgrounds and those who were not fully immunized. Common clinical signs included pallor (77.89%), developmental delay (73.68% of those with developmental delay had Vitamin B12 deficiency), and tremors. Complicated SAM was observed in 41.03% of the children. Inadequate breastfeeding with supplementary feeds was associated with a higher prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency (57.89% vs. 42.10% in exclusively breastfed children). Vitamin B12 deficiency was more common among children with microcephaly (83.33%) and severe wasting (82.57%), with statistically significant differences.

Conclusions: Vitamin B12 deficiency was prevalent in most children, regardless of age. Microcephaly, developmental delays, regression of milestones, hyperpigmentation, and nutritional tremor syndrome were also common in Vitamin B12-deficient children. Notably, three-fourths of exclusively breastfed infants up to six months had Vitamin B12 deficiency, likely due to maternal deficiency during pregnancy and lactation. This finding underscores the need for further research and potential Vitamin B12 supplementation during pregnancy, lactation, and early childhood to improve health outcomes.

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Introduction

The nutritional status of the people is internationally recognized as an indicator of national development. Nutrition is both an input and output indicator of the development process. A well-nourished, healthy workforce is a pre-condition for successful economic and social development; as such, promoting the nutritional status of the people is of utmost importance [1].

Severe acute malnutrition is defined by weight-for-height/length (Z- score below -3 SD of the median

WHO child growth standards), a mid-upper arm circumference < 11.5 cm, or the presence of nutritional edema [2].

SAM significantly increases the risk of death in children under five years of age. It can be a direct or indirect cause of child death by increasing the case fatality rate in children suffering from such common illnesses as diarrhea, acute respiratory infections, malaria, and measles [3].

The prevalence of severe acute malnutrition (SAM) among preschool children has been steadily rising in India over the last two decades. The National Family Health Survey-3 (NFHS-3) increased from 6.6% in 2005–2006 to 7.5% in NFHS-4 in 2015–2016. According to the most recent NFHS-5 survey (2019–2021), covering 36 states and union territories (UTs), the prevalence continues to be an alarming 7.7%. In India, an estimated 8.1 million (7.5%) children under the age of 5 are affected by severe acute malnutrition and are responsible for nearly 0.6 million deaths. According to data provided under National Family Health Survey-5 {NFHS-5,2021-2022}, the underweight prevalence rate was 35.8% and 63%; 58% and 16% of the children were malnourished, wasted, and stunted, respectively [4].

Micro- and macronutrient deficiencies (folic acid, Vitamin B12, Magnesium, Zinc, fat-soluble vitamins like Vitamin A, D, E, K; selenium, copper, Phosphorus, Calcium, Potassium, Sodium, Biotin, Niacin, Riboflavin, Thiamine) often coexist in severe malnutrition, and their impact on morbidity and mortality may be intertwined or compounded.

Children with cobalamin deficiency often present with manifestations ranging from weakness, lethargy, failure to thrive, microcephaly, pallor, glossitis, hyperpigmentation of skin, vomiting, diarrhea, and icterus. Neurological manifestations, manifesting as developmental regression, tremors, Poor academic performance, seizures, and sensory deficits, are most detrimental for a growing child. Maternal Vitamin B12 deficiency, leading to less Vitamin B12 secretion through breast milk, may be an independent risk factor for neural tube defects.

This study determined the clinical profile of SAM patients, the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency, and the clinical manifestations in these children.

Materials & Methods

Inclusion Criteria

All children aged 1–60 months suffering from severe acute malnutrition whose parents consented to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Age of children below one month of age and above 60 months of age.
- Parents not consenting.
- Blood transfusion received in the past six months.
- Intake of multivitamins and iron folic acid in the past six months.

Study Design and Settings

Inclusion Criteria

A hospital-based, observational, prospective study was done on 95 severely malnourished children admitted to the hospital over 12 months from July

2022 to June 2023. Children aged 1–60 months were enrolled in the study. Children who had received a blood transfusion in the past six months and those with a history of multivitamins and iron folic acid intake in the past six months were excluded from the study. A detailed socio-economic, feeding, and development history was obtained. Vitals like pulse, respiratory rate, heart rate, and temperature were recorded. Detailed anthropometric measurements were taken using standard methods. Children were classified according to weight for length/height Z score (WHZ) criteria as per WHO child growth standards charts (Multicentre Growth Reference Study, MGRS) as Z score of $< -3SD$ as severe acute malnutrition. The Trivandrum Development Screening Chart assessed the developmental status of the children. 51-item were used to assess the cognitive and motor milestones of children included in the study. If the child could complete any items to the left of the line, then there would be no delay in that item. If an item lies to the left of the line and the child cannot complete it, then an item delay is assumed.

Blood samples were collected at admission to measure plasma vitamin B. Vitamin B12 levels were estimated by electrochemi-luminescence (ECL) procedure using a COBAS e411 analyzer. A cut-off value below 100 pg/ml was considered deficient, between 100–200 pg/ml was considered borderline, and above 200 pg/ml was considered sufficient.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using SPSS (Chi-square test, T-test, percentage, mean, and standard deviation). Before starting the study, proper ethical clearance was obtained from the institution's Ethical Committee. Patients were enrolled after written and informed consent from their parents.

Results

Among 95 children enrolled in the study. 48 (50.52%) were Male, and 47(49.47%) were females. Out of 48 males, 42(87.50%) were vitamin B12 deficient, and out of 47 females, 32(68.08%) were vitamin B12 deficient. Vitamin B12 deficiency was more common among male children. Most of the SAM children, 77 (81.05%), were below 3 years of age. 74(77.88%) had deficiency of Vitamin B12 and 21(22.10%) had normal levels. Twenty-six children belonged to the upper and middle socioeconomic groups (27.35%), and 69 (72.68%) belonged to the lower socioeconomic group. Vitamin B12 was more commonly seen in children belonging to lower socioeconomic groups. Vitamin B12 deficiency among non-immunized, partially immunized, and completely immunized children were 21(95.45%), 34(91.89%), and 19(52.77%) children, respectively.

Table 1: Association of Baseline characteristics with Vitamin B 12 levels in Participants (N=95)

Characteristics	Vitamin B12 Levels		Total	P-value
	<200 pg/ml	>200 pg/ml		
Age (mo)				
1-6	18(75%)	6(25.01%)	24(25.26%)	
7-12	19(84.60%)	7(26.92%)	26(27.36%)	
13-36	23(85.18%)	4(14.81%)	27(28.42%)	
37-60	14(77.76%)	4(22.22%)	18(18.94%)	
Sex				
Male	42(87.50%)	6(28.57%)	48(50.52%)	0.001
Female	32(68.08%)	15(71.42%)	47(49.47%)	
Socio-economic Status				
Upper (Score≥15)	3(37.50%)	5(62.50%)	8(8.4%)	0.007
Middle (Score 11-15)	17(94.44%)	1(1.05%)	18(18.95%)	
Lower (Score≤10)	54(78.62%)	15(15.78%)	69(72.68%)	
Immunization Status				
Non immunized	21(95.45%)	1(4.54%)	22(23.15%)	0.0002
Partially Immunized	34(91.89%)	3(8.10%)	37(38.94%)	
Completely Immunized	19(52.77%)	17(47.22%)	36(37.89%)	

Head Circumference	Vitamin B12 Levels		Total	P-Value
	<200 pg/ml	>200 pg/ml		
<-3SD	50(83.33%)	10(16.66%)	60(63.15%)	0.0001
>-3SD	24(68.57%)	11(31.42%)	35(36.84%)	
Weight for height				
<-3SD for age	48(82.75%)	10(17.24%)	58(61.05%)	0.005
>-3SD for age	26(70.27%)	11(29.72%)	37(38.95%)	
Feeding Practices				
Exclusive Breast Feeding up to 6 months	29(72.50%)	11(27.50%)	40(42.10%)	0.015
Breast Feeding inadequate with Supplementary feed	45(60.81%)	10(47.61%)	55(57.89%)	
Clinical Features				
Hyperpigmentation	17(100%)	0(0)	17(17.89%)	0.91
Pallor	42(67.74%)	20(32.25%)	62(65.26%)	0.8
Tremor	28(100%)	0(0)	28(29.47%)	0.069
Nutritional Tremor Syndrome	28(100%)	0(0)	28(29.47%)	0.001
Developmental Delay	28(73.68%)	10(26.31%)	38(40%)	0.67

Discussion

During the study period, ninety-five children were studied; 74(77.88%) had a deficiency of Vitamin B12, and 21(22.10%) had normal levels. The deficiency in Vitamin B12 was observed in 18(75%), 19(84.60%), 23(85.18%), 14(77.76%) children in the age group of 1-6 months, 7-12 months, 13-36 months and 49-60 months respectively. Vitamin B12 deficiency was primarily seen in the ages of 7-12 months and 13-36 months. Goyal S et al. [5] had similar observations in their study. Kalyan G et al. (6), in their research on 210 healthy children of 6 to 24 months, observed that 37.6% were found to be cobalamin deficient.

Of 48 males, 42 (87.50%) were vitamin B12 deficient, and out of 47 females, 32 (68.08%) were vitamin B12 deficient. A similar result was obtained in another study conducted by Vaid A et al. [7], where 53.57% of male subjects and 65% of female subjects were deficient in Vitamin B12. This result was also supported by Yahikhomba T et al. [8].

In the present study, 26 children belong to the Upper and Middle socioeconomic groups (27.35%), and 69(72.68%) belong to the lower socioeconomic group. Vitamin B12 deficiency was more commonly seen in children belonging to lower socioeconomic strata. The difference in the prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency in different socioeconomic groups

was statistically significant (p -value 0.007). A slightly similar study by Goyal S et al. ⁽⁵⁾ showed that, of 30 (37.5%) vitamin B12 deficient children, 26 (86.66%) belong to lower socio-economic status and 4 (13.33%) to middle socio-economic status. A large proportion of subjects belong to the Lower socio-economic classes, maybe due to neglect, social stigma, delayed health-seeking of the parent, poverty, and low maternal education.

In the present study, 36(37.89%)children were completely immunized, 37 (38.94%) were partially immunized, and 22 (23.15%)children did not receive any immunization. 21 (95.45%), 34 (91.89%), and 19 (52.77%) children with Non-immunized status, partially immunized status, and Completely Immunized status had a deficiency in Vitamin B12 serum levels, respectively. A study by Murthy KA et al. [9] found that 83.30% of children had up-to-date immunization while 16.70% had incomplete immunization; they found it to be not statistically significant.

In the present study, 60(63.15%) children with SAM had Head circumference less than -3SD. 35(36.84%) children had head circumference more than -3SD. More children, 83.33%, with Vitamin B12 deficiency had head circumference less than -3SD. Patel B et al. [10] found that 82% of children with Vitamin B12 deficiency had microcephaly.

In the present study, 58 children (61.05%)had Weight for height/length less than -3SD, while 37 children (38.95%)had Weight for height/length more than -3SD. Among children with WFH <-3SD, 48 children (82.57%) had a deficiency in Vitamin B12 levels, while only 10 (17.24%)had normal Vitamin B12 levels. Vitamin B12 deficiency was more common among SAM children with severe wasting. This difference is statistically significant (p -value 0.005). Severe wasting was more often seen in Vitamin B12 deficient children; this is consistent with the findings by Yahikhomba T et al. [11], where 82.35% of the children with Vitamin B12 deficiency had weight for height < -3SD. Similarly, Goyal S et al. [5] observed stunting in 73.33% of Vitamin B12 deficient children.

Among 95 children enrolled, 74(77.89%) had vitamin B12 deficiency. Vitamin B12 deficiency was seen even among exclusively breastfed infants; 72.50% of infants exclusively breastfed for six months had Vitamin B12 deficiency. Goyal S et al. found out that in vitamin B12 deficient children, 17 (56.66%) were still predominantly breastfeeding, and 11 (36.66%) had delayed introduction of complementary feeding (beyond six months). The high prevalence (72.50%) of Vitamin B12 deficiency in infants below six months who were exclusively breastfed may be because of the high prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency among

pregnant women. [12,13] and hence lower accumulation of Vitamin B12 in breast milk.

Vitamin B12 deficiency was frequent in exclusively breastfed children, 29 out of 40. This may be because of the high prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency in the general population and pregnant females. The prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency among pregnant women was 74.1% [13], and among the general population, it was 47.19% [14]. This is a significant observation and has long-term social implications.

Conclusion

The study revealed that most of the children (81.06%) with Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) were under three years old, with a majority (72.63%) from rural areas. Anemia affected 77.89% of these children, and 41.03% had complicated SAM. Notably, 77.89% of the children had Vitamin B12 deficiency, linked to conditions such as microcephaly, developmental delays, and nutritional tremor syndrome. The deficiency was also common in exclusively breastfed infants (72.50%), likely due to maternal Vitamin B12 deficiency. These findings suggest more extensive studies to assess the potential benefits of Vitamin B12 supplementation during pregnancy, lactation, and early childhood to improve health outcomes for mothers and children.

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